

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Some Organic Compounds by Manganese(III) Sulphate

FIROZ AHMAD, VIKRAM S. BASWANI and SATENDRA KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 29 January 1979, revised 19 March 1980, accepted 9 April 1980

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of tartaric acid, malic acid, cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol by manganese(III) in sulphuric acid has been investigated spectrophotometrically. The reaction shows first order dependence, in the presence of low (0.01-0.15M) Mn^{II} concentration and second order in the presence of high (0.4-0.6M) Mn^{II} concentration, on $[Mn^{III}]$. The rate of oxidation is slightly increased by increasing $[H^+]$. The energy and entropy of activation are calculated in both the conditions. It is suggested that in the oxidation of hydroxy compounds by Mn^{III} , deprotonation of oxidation product is the rate determining step at low $[Mn^{II}]$.

OXIDATION by manganic compounds have been extensively studied by Waters and Wells¹⁻⁴.

Except the oxidation of cyclohexanol⁵, almost all oxidations by Mn^{III} show a retarding effect of Mn^{II} . Rosseinsky⁶ has reported that the oxidation of mercurous ion by Mn^{III} involves an equilibrium,

He proposed that the oxidation of Hg^I precedes by an attack of Mn^{IV} . The retardation can also be explained in terms of equilibrium (ii) and this has been verified in the oxidation of Malonic acid⁷.

The two electron transfer scheme for the oxidation of alcohols⁸ is based on the fact that its characteristics are similar to the oxidation of alcohols by chromic acid. Nevertheless it appears to be unjustified to assume that Mn^{IV} should always behave as a two electron oxidant and therefore the above explanation for the retardation effect of Mn^{II} should be taken as a specific case. It is evident from the survey of oxidation studies involving manganic ion that the effect of manganous ion on the kinetics of such reactions has not been fully understood⁷⁻¹⁶. In order to study this characteristic behaviour of Mn^{II} , this work was undertaken. A series of preliminary tests were carried out with different organic compounds. In course of these investigations it was observed that oxidation of some hydroxy compounds shows the retarding effect by the addition of Mn^{II} ions and also at some optimum $[Mn^{II}]$, there was a change in the order of reaction. Results and experimental details of these investigations are presented here.

Experimental

Materials and methods : All chemicals used were either reagent grade or of certified purity. In all kinetic experiments $Mn(III)$ were prepared in H_2SO_4 by Ubbelohde's method¹⁷. Double distilled water was used in all kinetic runs. Second distillation was done with potassium permanganate.

Kinetics : The reaction was initiated by mixing the reactant solutions which were equilibrated at 20° unless otherwise stated. An aliquot of the reaction mixture was taken in a known volume of nearly 3M ice-cold H_2SO_4 , and the rate of disappearance of Mn^{III} measured at 510 nm on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20. The concentration of Mn^{III} was read from the calibration curve obtained by plotting $[Mn^{III}]$ against absorbance. In most of the cases the reaction was followed to well over 85% of its completion. The duplicate rate measurements are reproducible to $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant k_{obsd} ($l. mol^{-1} min^{-1}$) reported here were obtained from the slope of the plots of time against $1/[Mn^{III}]$ and the first order rate k_{obsd} (min^{-1}) were obtained from the slope of the plots of time against $\log [Mn^{III}]$.

Results and Discussion

It is found that if $[Mn^{II}]$ in the reaction mixture is less than 10 times of $[Mn^{III}]$, the reaction follows first order kinetics for the oxidation of tartaric acid, malic acid, cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol (Table 1). But if the concentration of Mn^{II} in the reaction mixture is more than 16 times of $[Mn^{III}]$, the reaction is second order in $[Mn^{III}]$ for the oxidation of tartaric acid, malic acid and cyclohexanol but zero order for allyl alcohol (Table 2). Oxidation of some other organic compounds such as formic acid,

TABLE 1—THE EFFECT OF Mn^{II} ON THE REACTION RATE UNDER FIRST ORDER CONDITION

$[H_2SO_4]=3.0M$ for all compounds ; Temp. = 20° for tartaric and malic acid ; 50° and 45° for cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol ($[Mn^{II}]+[ZnSO_4]=0.152M$)

(i) [Tartaric acid] = 0.913M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.026M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.013M$
0.002	7.90	8.00
0.102	2.50	2.40
0.152	2.00	1.96

(ii) [Malic acid] = 0.0083M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.017M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.0083M$
0.002	12.14	12.00
0.102	2.00	2.00
0.152	1.84	1.84

(iii) [Cyclohexanol] = 0.013M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.025M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.013M$
0.002	1.20	1.18
0.102	0.36	0.35
0.152	0.30	0.31

(iv) [Allyl alcohol] = 0.10M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.017M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.0083M$
0.002	4.40	4.40
0.102	2.08	2.04
0.152	1.76	1.73

formaldehyde, maleic and fumaric acids, malonic and pyruvic acids, do not show the change of order but there is only retardation by Mn^{II} .

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[Mn^{II}]$ ON THE REACTION RATE UNDER SECOND ORDER CONDITION

Conditions are same as in Table 1 ; All the k_{obs} in ($1 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) for tartaric acid, malic acid and cyclohexanol and k_{obs} in ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) for allyl alcohol,

($[Mn^{II}]+[ZnSO_4]=0.603M$)

(i) [Tartaric acid] = 0.013M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	k_{obs}	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.026M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.013M$
0.403	0.60	0.62
0.503	0.40	0.40
0.603	0.40	0.40

(ii) [Malic acid] = 0.0083M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	k_{obs}	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.017M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.0083M$
0.403	0.78	0.80
0.503	0.76	0.78
0.603	0.76	0.78

(iii) [Cyclohexanol] = 0.013M

$[Mn^{II}]M$	k_{obs}	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.025M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.013M$
0.403	0.091	0.090
0.503	0.083	0.083
0.603	0.083	0.083

(iv) [Allyl alcohol] = 0.10

$[Mn^{II}]M$	k_{obs}	
	$[Mn^{III}]=0.017M$	$[Mn^{III}]=0.0083M$
0.403	1.66	1.67
0.503	1.64	1.60
0.603	1.64	1.60

Hydrogen ion concentration was varied with H_2SO_4 in the range 1.0-3.5M at constant $\mu=4.0M$ ($NaHSO_4$), in the presence of low and high Mn^{II} (Table 3). The rate increased with the increase of

 TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$ ON THE OXIDATION RATE UNDER LOW AND HIGH Mn^{II} CONDITIONS

$[Mn^{III}]=0.015M ; 0.017M ; 0.013M ; 0.008M$ for tartaric, malic, cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol respectively ; $\mu=3.50M$ for all compounds. Temperature are same as in Table 1

(i) [Tartaric acid] = 0.015M

$[H_2SO_4]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	At low $[Mn^{II}](0.002M)$	At high $[Mn^{II}](0.6M)$
1.50	7.3	0.35
2.50	8.3	0.42
3.50	8.6	0.44

(ii) [Malic acid] = 0.008M

$[H_2SO_4]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	At low $[Mn^{II}](0.002M)$	At high $[Mn^{II}](0.6M)$
1.00	9.00	0.58
2.00	9.50	0.68
3.00	10.25	0.76

(iii) [Cyclohexanol] = 0.013M

$[H_2SO_4]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	At low $[Mn^{II}](0.002M)$	At high $[Mn^{II}](0.6M)$
2.50	1.10	0.06
3.00	1.25	0.08
3.50	1.50	0.12

(iv) [Allyl alcohol] = 0.10M

$[H_2SO_4]M$	$k_{obs}(min^{-1})$	
	At low $[Mn^{II}](0.002M)$	At high $[Mn^{II}](0.6M)$
1.50	2.70	1.25
2.50	3.10	1.45
3.50	4.80	1.70

$[H^+]$. The variation of oxidation rate with temperature was studied at four temperatures. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ against $1/T$ were linear and various activation parameters were evaluated, using Arrhenius and Eyring equations with a linear least squares treatment, in the presence of low as well as high Mn^{II} in the reaction mixture (Table 4). Our observations indicate that the oxidation of hydroxy

 TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR BOTH CONDITIONS (Low and High Mn^{II}) OF REACTIONS : ΔE^* in K cal mol^{-1} and ΔS^* in cal $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$

Reductant	At low $[Mn^{II}]=0.002M$		At high $[Mn^{II}]=0.602M$	
	ΔE^*	ΔS^*	ΔE^*	ΔS^*
Tartaric acid	28.0 ± 1.4	30.0 ± 3.5	27.8 ± 1.2	29.1 ± 4.0
Malic acid	22.9 ± 1.3	22.4 ± 4.3	23.9 ± 1.8	16.7 ± 6.0
Cyclohexanol	24.7 ± 1.8	15.9 ± 5.4	29.2 ± 0.5	24.6 ± 1.4
Allyl alcohol	2.6 ± 0.4	13.3 ± 1.7	22.0 ± 0.3	9.2 ± 0.9

compound involves a free radical mechanism, and show retarding effect on increasing the concentration of Mn^{II} . Moreover, the oxidation of these hydroxy compounds undergo a transition of order with respect to manganic ion at some Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} ratio. Our preliminary studies with a large number of organic compounds show that this type of transition

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF THE OXIDATION RATE ON [ORGANIC SUBSTRATE] UNDER LOW AND HIGH [Mn^{II}] CONDITIONS

[Mn^{III}]=0.013M, 0.008M, 0.013M and 0.008M for tartaric, malic, cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol respectively ; [H₂SO₄]=3.0M for all compounds ; Temperature=20° for tartaric and malic acid ; 50° and 45° for cyclohexanol and allyl alcohol

	At low [Mn ^{II}]=0.002M k _{obs} (min ⁻¹)	At high [Mn ^{II}]=0.4M k _{obs} (1 mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
(Tartaric acid) (M)		
0.008	5.0	0.37
0.013	8.1	0.63
0.018	11.0	0.87
0.023	13.9	1.10
0.028	17.1	1.30
(Malic acid) (M)		
0.008	12.0	0.81
0.013	19.4	1.28
0.018	27.2	1.76
0.023	35.0	2.10
0.028	42.0	2.42
(Cyclohexanol) (M)		
0.008	0.8	0.04
0.013	1.2	0.09
0.018	1.7	0.13
0.023	2.1	0.16
0.028	2.7	0.20
(Allyl alcohol) (M)		k _{obs} (mol l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
0.10	4.4	1.70
0.15	6.8	2.50
0.20	9.0	3.30
0.25	11.4	4.00
0.30	14.0	5.00

is observed with hydroxy compounds only. The overall rate law being,

$$-d[Mn^{III}]/dt = k_1 [Mn^{III}]/[Mn^{II}] + k_2 [Mn^{III}]^2 / [Substrate].$$

It appears that at low [Mn^{II}], the first term is significant and reaction is true first order in [Mn^{III}]. It is evident from any typical run that reaction does not follow a first order kinetics after certain percentage of reaction. This could probably be one of the reasons as why Waters and others have used initial rates to determine order of the reaction instead of using integrated order equations. When the reaction is first order, there is a retardation of manganous ion (Table 1). However, when the reaction is second order, at high concentration of Mn^{II} (0.4-0.6M), there is no effect on second order rate constant (Table 2) as there is neither a change in the stoichiometry of the reaction nor in the nature of product obtained under the two conditions. The effect of [H⁺] on the reaction rate is positive at low as well as at high [Mn^{II}]. This would probably

suggest that hydrolyzed Mn^{III} is equilibrated with Mn^{III} in the reaction medium,

It is also noted that an intermediate complex is formed during the course of reaction observed in UV range (at 275 nm) when the reaction is carried out in the presence of high [Mn^{II}]. In view of these observations a possible mechanism of these reactions could be given as :

at low [Mn^{II}] equilibrium (3) is well established and equilibrium concentration of [complex]₁ is very low. Under these conditions step (4) which signifies deprotonation of the [complex]₂ represents major reaction path and determines the rate of the reaction, where the subscript 1 refers to stoichiometric concentrations and K_h is the equilibrium constant for Mn³⁺ hydrolysis (reaction 1),

$$\text{Thus, } r.r. = k_4 [complex]_2$$

$$= K_2 K_3 k_4 \frac{[Mn^{III}]_T [Substrate]_T}{[Mn^{II}](1 + K_h[H^+]^{-1})}$$

However, at high [Mn^{II}] the rate of backward reaction of equilibrium (3) dominates too strongly over the step (4) and therefore this reaction path is completely choked. There is an accumulation of the [complex]₁ and step (6) becomes the rate determining step, giving

$$r.r. = k_6 [complex]_1 [Mn^{III}]_T / (1 + K_h[H^+]^{-1}) \\ = \frac{K_2 k_6 [Mn^{III}]^2_T [Substrate]_T}{(1 + K_h[H^+]^{-1})^2}$$

The oxidation of allyl alcohol seems to follow a different mechanism. In this case the reaction is found to become zero order in [Mn^{III}] at high [Mn^{II}], and there is no effect of [Mn^{II}] on the rate constant under this condition. The reaction shows first order dependence on [H⁺] at low as well as at high [Mn^{II}]. It appears that the protonated allyl

alcohol is the reactive species which forms a complex with the oxidant. At high $[Mn^{II}]$, the formation of this protonated species becomes the rate determining step.

The probable mechanism being,

At low $[Mn^{II}]$ step (3) competes well with the backward reaction of equilibrium (2) and step (3) is the rate determining, giving

$$-d[Mn^{III}]_T/dt = k_s [\text{complex}]$$

$$= K_2 K_a k_s \frac{[Mn^{III}]_T [C_3H_5OH]_T}{(1 + Kh[H^+]^{-1})(1 + 1/K_a[H^+])[Mn^{II}]}$$

However, at high $[Mn^{II}]$ equilibrium (2) is predominantly on the left-hand side and so is equilibrium (1). Thus, the rate of protonation of allyl alcohol becomes the rate determining step, giving

$$-d[Mn^{III}]_T/dt = \frac{K_a [C_3H_5OH]_T}{(1 + 1/K_a[H^+])}$$

A similar scheme of reaction has been proposed by Drummond and Waters¹⁸ for the oxidation of

ketones by manganic pyrophosphate¹. The mechanism of the reaction suggests that deprotonation of the substrate follows rather than precedes the reduction of manganic ion.

References

1. A. Y. DRUMMOND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 435.
2. C. F. WELLS, *Nature*, 1965, 205, 693.
3. C. F. WELLS and G. DAVIES, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, 63, 2737.
4. C. F. WELLS and G. DAVIES, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1968, 64, 3069.
5. J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 832.
6. D. R. ROSSEINSKY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1181.
7. W. A. WATERS and T. J. KEMP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1489.
8. J. H. MIRZ, G. STAFFORD and W. A. WATERS *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 638.
9. W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2129.
10. H. LAND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2121.
11. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 339.
12. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1489.
13. P. LEVESLEY and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.
14. H. LAND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2129.
15. A. Y. DRUMMOND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 501.
16. A. Y. DRUMMOND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3119.
17. A. R. J. P. UBBELOHDE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1605.
18. A. Y. DRUMMOND and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 497.